

KAZAKH LANGUAGE LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES ARE FRUITFUL USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN ORGANIZATION

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Abstract. *The level of creative thinking of junior high school students, teaching the young generation to speak clearly, clearly, impressively and artistically in their native language is the main issue.*

Keywords: *basic course of the Kazakh language, choose methods, fill in the grids, reward with high score, game winner.*

Introduction

It is clear that the level of education of elementary school students in Kazakh language is a problem that has been on our minds for a long time. Often, the level of creative thinking of elementary school students is one of the main problems.

In many cases we liken the student to a person standing in the middle of a river looking for water. The river is full of water - the child is thirsty. Our terms are full of words, if the student's vocabulary is small, there are few words. Such a situation is, first of all, closely related to the content of Kazakh language education.

Research materials and methodology

Educational content is reflected in curricula, programs and textbooks, as well as study-calendar applications. The effectiveness of teaching the Kazakh language is closely related to many consequences. Among them, the teaching of the Kazakh language has an important and leading place. This is because, first of all, productivity is closely related to the issue of "What to teach" to students. It is possible to find an answer to the question "What should be taught" only if the list of knowledge and skills corresponding to the necessary knowledge that students should have from the teaching of the Kazakh language is correctly established. So, first of all, fruitfulness is directly related to these two consequences.

The main goal of teaching the Kazakh language in primary schools should be defined as follows: through the Kazakh language, students of primary school should develop the skills of creativity, independent thinking, the ability to read the results of opinions in oral and written forms correctly, clearly and at a pace. In Kazakh language exercises, the main importance should be focused not on the grammatical structure of the language, but on improving their vocabulary, using words correctly and appropriately, and expanding their skills to express their opinions in a situational way.

The issue of teaching the young generation to speak clearly, comprehensibly, impressively and artistically in their native language is of primary importance. The task of educating students to be literate, able to express their opinion correctly and freely, with a culture of speech style, is carried out in the primary school at the primary school. A student who has mastered the style of speech, keeps his language from becoming sloppy, and can use all the possibilities of his language as needed, of course, learns other subjects easily and quickly and fully, and his desire for education and culture grows stronger in them.

In the elementary course of the Kazakh language, special attention is paid to the development of speech skills and tactics, orthographic and spelling literacy, working on words and their meanings, and the ability to use words correctly and appropriately in the process of speaking.

"In a democratic society, children, in general, are brought up so that everyone can think freely. If children do not learn to think freely, the teaching will be less effective. Of course, education is necessary, but education is in its own way. own opinion is also a great wealth..." said our President, emphasizing the importance of the future generation to grow up to be educated and qualified, having their own and free opinion.

Of course, one of the prerequisites for educating the young generation as a perfect person is to conduct the teaching and upbringing process based on modern requirements, to rely on the principles of continuity, to rationally use advanced pedagogical technologies, and to organize classes in a way that makes effective use of information technologies.

The selection of methods based on the features of the subjects learned in the primary grade Kazakh language classes creates opportunities for the students to hold discussions and debates on the subjects and express their opinions freely.

In this process, it is required to develop more language wealth, supplement the needs due to getting used to language training exercises, pay special attention to the correct selection of ways and methods that direct them to their own thinking.

In order for students to master each topic, it is necessary to be able to choose the right methods and methods that ensure the effectiveness of teaching, based on their age characteristics and opportunities to learn the Kazakh language. Only then we will achieve the desired result.

The effectiveness of teaching the subject "Kazakh language" in primary classes is closely related to many consequences. Undoubtedly, taking into account the psychological characteristics of students and learning opportunities, the list of tasks and methods that correspond to the content and purpose of Kazakh language teaching, All the consequences, such as the establishment of a pedagogical association between the teacher and the student, the appropriate selection of tools used in the lesson, are related to ensuring productivity.

Among such consequences, the content of teaching the Kazakh language is considered an important and leading consequence. This is because productivity is primarily about teaching students "What to teach?" closely related to the problem. "What kind of teaching should be done" only if the list of necessary knowledge that students should have from Kazakh language teaching and the list of knowledge and skills corresponding to that knowledge is correctly defined. it is possible to find an answer to the question. So, first of all, productivity will be directly related to these two factors.

"What should be taught?" and "What kind of training?" consequences, two manifestations of the same process are calculated. They are so closely connected with each other that one without the other has no fruitful meaning.

The effectiveness of teaching the Kazakh language is related, first of all, to the content of the teaching, that is, to the list of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities provided to students in that subject, secondly, the publication of pedagogical technologies in the teaching process is closely connected with the tools that realize the students' interest in learning the Kazakh language, their desire to learn.

Organization of Kazakh language lessons in various non-traditional forms in primary classes is considered the most important requirement of pedagogical technology. Here is one of

those non-traditional lesson forms - a lesson called "Travel to the world of knowledge learned or being learned". Students travel to the world of knowledge while sitting in the classroom. The teacher divides the educational tasks set during the lesson into four to five "stations". Pupils who overcome all educational difficulties are considered to be the owners of the state of knowledge.

One form of informal lessons is the game lesson. In these lessons, each task is organized in the form of a didactic game. When performing exercises on vowels and consonants, you can use games such as "Find consonant words", "Fill the given grids quickly", "Continue the list of words with double sounds". The organization of language tasks in the form of a competition encourages the task to turn into an interesting game, as a result of the game, it is possible to determine the winners and reward them.

Search results.

Here are some examples of didactic games:

Game "Find words that sound like the given words".

Students should change the given first, second and third sounds to create consonant words. Students who complete the task first without mistakes win the game. For example, find words that sound like cattle, cost, raft, ash, tone. First option view: Example: mal - mas, tal, zhal, manh, pan, dawn, dust, fat, mat, cal.

Ton - tol, mol, zhol, kol, sol, jon, kon, kos, tos, ton, end.

Kun - kul, kyn, kyl, lyk, tik, shik, sik, kum, shin, nuk, bird, ice, kuz, kum, kut, yut, ulu, ugu, tutu, kui, blood.

Sal - sel, number, las, kas, stone, young, cattle, asu, ala, grandpa, mother.

Ashes - zhul, sun, sol, moss, fur, load, owl, come, less, mine, zero, cut, leave, manure, blue, fall, autumn, wait, bury.

In the second option, the following can be used:

Kol - ash, hand - slave, ton - ton, chat - account, chong - dust, cattle - abundance, sal - left, will - full, jal - road, stay - hand, say - soi, zai - destroy, kai - cow, odd - tuk, sak - suk, jan - jon, jaya - yoya, koya - kuya, saya - soya, mother - asa, father - grandmother, brother - grandfather, tas - tos, ara - apa, ai - oi, wedding - thai, value - blood, no - jaw, suk - sok, needle - ime, esi - two, read - this, ile - drink, elu - egu.

In the third option, the following can be used:

mal - mat, manh, pan, dust, dawn, will, chal; mol - mil, elephant, syllabary, tongue; full - til, tal, shol, hand, road, left, mul, be; kal - kal, kal, kil, kul, zhul, tul, bul; left - sel, sen, seng, som, sok, number, sat, sak, sok, sik, siz, sym, syt, sau, sal, suk, sai, sap.

Didactic game "Fill the mysterious grids".

Pupils are tasked with filling in the blanks and making words that sound together. For example, it is required to continue the word tai to the word sai. Sample: tai, toi, oi, chai, koi, destroy, mai, soi, jay, kai, nai, lai, sai.

Suggested words:

1. Head, stone, as, eyebrow, young, double.

2. Ball, be, full, road, goal, mul, hal, hand.

"Continue the pairs of words" game.

Word sequences that are most likely to cause spelling mistakes when students write: September - September, album - album, razezd - razezd, khaharman - khakarman, April - April, ah - white, asphalt - asphalt, borsch - borsch, achy - ashi, tushchi - tushi given in the form of correct

and incorrect spelling. Students must explain which order of the given words is correct, why they are correct or why they are written incorrectly, in accordance with the rules. The student who is the first to express his opinion correctly will be awarded. About 10-15 of the given pairs of words should be hung on the blackboard in the form of sample noodles. If the student can guess all the given words correctly, he should be awarded with a high score without an additional task or question. This game can also be played on the board by dividing the class into groups. Each student in a row goes to the board, writes a pair of words and offers the chalk to another student. The game continues in this order.

Discussions.

"Make a list of words that are the same in both syllables" game.

In this game, students learn words that have the same vowel sound in both the first and second syllables, for example, cat, pсыk, kazakh, kilik, kalyk, salak, tabok, zatak, jaynar, kaynar, school, bucket, universe, pen, body, cream, shaft, knowledge, hook, weapon, Yanak, goal, fold, limit, sieve, area, drive, pasture, career, jansak, zaysan, comb, Kalmyk, Kyrgyz, sky, shout, kaspak, pot, paper, kumyz, The task is to find words such as food, man, step, sail, youth, child, city, field, mirror, and many others and complete the list of words in the specified amount of time.

The students who find the most words in the set amount are called the winners of the game.

Domino game.

This game can be played in the following order: one student says a word, the word that ends with a letter, another student must say the word that starts with that letter. This game continues in the same way. Sample: in option 1, a specified time limit is set orally, the student who could not continue in the game leaves the row, and the remaining student becomes the winner. The speech of the student should correspond to the purpose and content of the topic. For example, if you are learning a series of vowel sounds, it is necessary to have a sequence of words that can be used to make syllables, match the spelling of the vowels in the syllables, and combine and connect with the advanced topics.

In option 2, students try to get high marks in a competitive manner in order to avoid spelling mistakes in writing. When working with small groups, one of the group members will try to write a series of words starting with the letter i, and the other will try to write a series of words starting with the letter y. Here you have to write on the board according to the number of small groups, or the groups are asked to write on a clean white sheet provided in advance. For example; According to the vowels i and y: work - door - person - businessman - order - shirt - shoe - boot - cotton - Siberia - rawish - mosquito - smell - fat - leech - sorry - rawan - March - tyrant - teacher - gun - tymak, curd - reed - rumor - horror - well - behavior - spoon - peg - jar - sixty - patience - grace - Egypt - role - cheese - small - hanger - shubar - messenger - throw - thanks - tymau - spawn - kimyran - object - Nurman - Naiman - Nasyr - Republic - Grain - Winter - Handful - Excuse - Uyk - Eagle - Proverb - Throw.

"Tracking letter" game.

The teacher instructs the students to write a word based on the given letter. For example, the teacher instructs you to write examples of the appearance of that letter at the beginning of a word. He clearly sets a time of 2-3 minutes to complete the task. Pupils write: happiness, singing, shalgu, shalgi, shama, tiredness, sharapat, shar, chew, sharayna, shamala, shanak, shapagat, Sharipa, Sharip, Sharigul, Shamshiya, shanshar, shat, chak, shok, shoktanu, sholak, sholpy, fork, tent, invite, invitation, chess, Shanghai, kalkalu, confusion, teapot, bucket, shopor, shushu,

sholshanu, ivy, pinch, dew, shit, shir, shirm, truth, shymir, pants, Shalkar, Shalkiiz, Shu, desert, desert, sheker, sheke, master, limit, infinity, pig, peak, dust, lamp, hair, glass, bill, Shamshat, peak, shake, sharkat, shirket, gnat, rot, grass, gravel, circle, shepherd, shapshan. The mentioned didactic game type can be used individually and in small groups from the following options.

Option 1: within 2-3 minutes, at the request of the teacher, students must write a sequence of words that appear at the beginning of the word in the presence of the specified control letter. For example; In the presence of the letter Sh. Individually, all students write as many words as they want within 2-3 minutes. The student who finds the most words starting with the letter Ш and writes without mistakes will be awarded.

In option 2: students who have completed the work individually are given a task of grouping to control the degree of mastery of the principle of making syllables from which letters by dividing words starting with the letter ш into syllables. For example; A competition will be organized on the content of who can make as many word sequences in 2-3 minutes depending on the number of vowel letters after the letter ш followed by the vowels а, б, и, ы, е, э, у, у, у, и, о. Here, students are instructed to work on one vowel letter for every 2-3 depending on the number of vowel letters. At the end of the task, the students who found the most and completed it without mistakes will be the winners.

In the 3rd option: the students who have done it individually will now classify the written word chains according to the number of syllables within 2-3 minutes on the third keyboard, compete in the content of who found more syllable words than other students and was able to write without mistakes, the students who completed the task perfectly will be awarded.

4 - on the keyboard: the students as a team now group together according to the rules by asking questions about how many words they found in the sequence of words starting with the letter sh, and how many of them are the names of people, Earth - water, action - movement, city, plant, animals, insects, and based on the "Branch" method. brings to one channel. In conclusion, through a single didactic game, students improve their skills of performing according to the rules, their vocabulary through the exchange of new information, listen to each other, discuss, come to a common opinion on the basis of this, get organized, write beautifully, have an opinion with its own meaning, and express it in a timely manner. are brought up to protect.

In option 5: sentences, short stories, small text composition using the "Insert" method, stories, proverbs, proverbs, riddles, riddles from extracurricular literature characteristic of the above-mentioned titles, read or memorize them, tasks such as telling the content should be assigned according to the students' level of acceptance and age characteristics. This didactic game can be organized in small groups in the same manner and according to the requirements, only here the main task of the teacher is to pay attention to the distribution of time, following the group members in a way that ensures the participation of everyone.

In the 6th option: the students have to write a sentence including 5-6 words within the time specified by the teacher's instruction or the requirement of another group, without listing the created words. Now the students should be able to relate the words they wrote, write meaningful sentences that express certain actions, underline the words used, and show them in a competitive way. Here, the student or team member who performs without mistakes and in the specified time becomes the winner. Below are examples of word sequences starting with the letter Ш ш:

Tea, Shalkiiz, Shalkar, tent, jackal, Shamil, Sharbanu, sharkat, chess, shashbau, ball, Sharipa, singing, confusion, joy, pants, crab, sledge, shunak, shot, shinygul, stick, hair, Shamshi, square,

ivy, glass foot, juice, sugar, pupil, sholak, Shokan, shaban, hat, shanak, zhizhik, glass, fir tree, hairdresser, teapot, teahouse, sharayna, adventure, shirpy, Shyntemir, shal, shit, sheke, chesh, schat, truth, fly, chew, Shymbai, shi, dust, chak, sham, parade, Shamshat, shangytpa, shankobyz, shayen, click, sock, shirkei, shiithey, circle, master, Shaygul, Sharip, rider, shabys, shatys, east, shepherd, wine, Shakir, smoke, locust, Shu, Shukyrkudyk, ladle, ladle, shopyr, shotyr, shukur, thank you, Shakhrisabz, Shafirken, shanyrak, Shatkal, shobdar, Shaitanat, Shymkent, church, ugly, rag, great-great, great-grandson, chil, Shamshiya, Sholpan, pike, Shomanai, chok, choku, chokpar, cast iron, candle, pig, champagne, Shanghai, puck, ski, Chingis, etc. b.

"Find the next generation" game.

In relation to the given syllables, the relevance of word formation is determined. The student who can make the most words will be awarded with "five". For example; ba, ta, ka, sa, ne, ke, ja, na... The given syllable must appear only at the beginning of the word.

1. ba: boy, grandfather, bazaar, fish, batyr, Babur, balausa, mud, batpan, bashir, bakir, velvet, predominate.
2. ta: talak, tartar, food, comb, branch, tape, taru, tarma, talkan, Tamara, tas, tara, tandoor, flood.
3. ka: spoon, katyk, reed, kazakh, kalymak, kasyk, kayrat, kash, kasym, gardin, karmak, kaymak, kashkir, fugitive.
4. sa: calm, treacherous, cold, sandugash, triumph, samal, watch, sarkyt, samarkant, samara, saira, number, sal, chest.
5. what: what, why, why, how many, some, nectar, why, German.
6. ke: kebis, perfect, kemis, leave, come, late, delay, late, came, leave, come, cut, leave, left, excused.
7. ja: jamal, closed, bed, stick, lie, close, hide, Jakyp, jal, zay, jap, young, youth, enemy, rain, rain, mint.
8. na: nanyam, nasyr, nan, naq, Nakyp, naryn, nala, marz, Nariman, Nagima, nasybai, nava, nar, Nartai.

Conclusion

Teaching students to write text is considered one of the requirements of the State Education Standard. Teaching elementary school students to write a text on the subject of the Kazakh language requires the use of several teaching tools. Compose oral or written texts for students based on pictures, prepare short written texts based on learned topics, develop individual abilities of students, create texts about observations, experiences, seen and heard events and situations, continue the text given in the starting part, They should learn to write texts on topics such as "My mother", "Motherland", "My mother tongue", learn the content of the genre of poetry presented in verses, be able to narrate, and be able to compose a text based on it. Thus, methods such as choosing the right teaching method for the effectiveness of teaching the Kazakh language in elementary grades, coming from the practical direction of the subject "Kazakh language" and encouraging more students to think and reason in the teaching process, implementing educational tasks, and using lesson forms that realize the need to know and learn in students are very important. is important.

Educational and didactic games play a crucial role in making the student a subject of the educational process. Didactic games organized in the Kazakh language encourage the learner to search, be creative, determine the significance of the event being learned, make judgments and conclusions. Educational games help every student to learn the ability to see himself, to express

his own opinion, to defend it, to complete the task with pleasure. In them: quickness, sensitivity, business, creativity, education, principles, independence, prudence and the initial manifestations of civility are forming.

Games organized in the Kazakh language can not only strengthen knowledge, but also teach memorization and repetition, support of the acquired knowledge in new situations, even if it is small, and finally use it in new scenes. In the lesson exercises, only the same or similar game - not limited to tasks, but perhaps more creativity - should strengthen the emphasis on tasks. This is because we should never forget that our goal is to meet the demands of the times and its directions and ways, and that the education of the perfect generation should be our main focus.

When organizing educational and didactic games, the subject teacher should choose them in accordance with the purpose and task of the subject, take into account the age and educational level of the students, the fact that the game is aimed at forming the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of the students.

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